

**EFFECTS OF UPSTREAM EXHAUST MANIFOLD ON THE FLOW FIELDS OF A
TURBOCHARGER RADIAL TURBINE**

<p>Shyang Maw Lim Competence Center for Gas Exchange (CCGEx) & Linné FLOW Center Department of Mechanics KTH Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden</p>	<p>Anders Dahkild Linné FLOW Center Department of Mechanics KTH Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden</p>	<p>Mihai Mihaescu Competence Center for Gas Exchange (CCGEx) & Linné FLOW Center Department of Mechanics KTH Royal Institute of Technology Stockholm, Stockholm, Sweden</p>
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ABSTRACT

This study was primarily motivated by limited analysis of the flow fields in a turbocharger turbine subjected to heat loss and highly non-isothermal pulsatile flow. In this study, we aimed to investigate the influence of exhaust manifold on the flow physics and the effects on turbine power under engine-like pulsatile flow conditions. Based on the predicted results by Detached Eddy Simulation (DES), qualitative and quantitative flow fields analysis in the scroll and the rotor's inlet were performed. At a specified geometry configuration and exhaust valve strategy, the main findings of our study were 1) The fundamental flow physics in the scroll is highly governed by the presence of upstream exhaust manifold, and therefore any flow field and unsteadiness analysis based on a set-up without the exhaust manifold should be interpreted with care, and 2) Reverse flow in some rotor's blade passages are observed during low mass flow rate and this attributes to turbine windmilling, i.e. negative turbine power. The outcomes of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the thermo-fluid physics associated with the presence of upstream exhaust manifold, which is often neglected in other studies. Furthermore, this study also provides the missing puzzle pieces associated with the customary pulsatile flow turbine research approach of ignoring the upstream exhaust manifold, and increase the awareness about the pros and cons of current state of the art.

INTRODUCTION

In turbocharged automotive engine, the exhaust gas is discharged into the turbine via an exhaust manifold, which is located at the downstream of the exhaust valves. The flow into the exhaust manifold is highly pulsatile as a result of

the opening-closing of the exhaust valves and the reciprocating piston motion. Due to space constraint, the exhaust manifold in an automotive engine has customarily compact design, i.e. small volume with multiple narrow and bend pipes. While exhaust manifold with smaller volume could preserve the available energy to the turbine better in theory, upstream geometry complexity also indicates that the turbine is inherently subjected to high degree of secondary flow and flow unsteadiness, in addition to periodic flow pulsation. Furthermore, heat transfer is also significant due to large temperature gradient between the hot side (exhaust manifold and turbine) and the environment. The magnitude of heat loss can be as large as 1.5 times the expansion work of the turbine at operating conditions corresponding to low engine speed [1].

The first detailed study of the performance of a pulse flow turbocharger turbine was conducted more than three decades ago [2]. Despite the integration of exhaust manifold with turbine in automotive engines, some researchers ignore its presence in their studies. Pulsatile flow test facility customarily has an electric-driven rotary pulse generator installed at the upstream of the turbine (e.g., see Refs. [3], [4]). By controlling the rotary motion of two counter rotating plates in the pulse generator, pulsatile flow that mimicking the shape and the frequency of the exhaust pulse as in the automotive engine is fed into the turbine via a straight pipe. The working fluid is electrically heated air of about 350 K to avoid condensation of water vapour and icing during expansion process in the turbine. On the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) side, since there is dependency on the measurement data in the aforementioned pulsatile test rig for boundary conditions, it is natural that most of the computational models found in open literature replicate the experiment setup with straight inlet pipe. Turbine inflow is assumed to be spatially uniform and

perpendicular to the inlet boundary in addition to adiabatic condition (e.g., see Refs. [5]–[7]). This type of experiment and numerical setups inherently signifies that the incoming secondary flow due to the presence of upstream exhaust manifold and the heat transfer phenomenon are not considered. Nevertheless, the simplifications mentioned above (i.e. straight inlet pipe and adiabatic condition) allow researchers to focus their analyses on the effects of flow pulsation on turbine performance under carefully controlled conditions. Up to date, it is generally to our knowledge that the performance map of a pulse flow turbine form hysteresis loop and it deviates from the steady flow characteristics (e.g., see Refs. [3], [8], [9]). Detailed velocity triangle analysis shows that instantaneous flow conditions at the inlet and outlet of the rotor change significantly over a pulse period, and this indicates that for most of the time, a pulsatile flow turbine operates far from its optimum, single design condition under the steady flow assumptions (e.g., see Refs. [10], [11]).

In a numerical work with high fidelity three-dimensional (3D) CFD, Hellström and Fuchs [12] integrated the exhaust manifold to a radial turbine in their adiabatic computational model, and their pulsatile flow computational results showed that the flow entering the turbine is highly non-uniform and disturbed by the secondary flow originated from the exhaust manifold. Realizing the missing of complex turbine inflow conditions in the state of the art discussed above, there exist efforts to introduce secondary flows in conjunction with flow pulsation at the turbine inlet. In a cold-flow pulsatile flow experiment, instead of using an exhaust manifold, Kalpakli et al. [13] simplified the physical problem by mounting a 90° bend pipe to the turbine inlet. Time-resolved stereoscopic particle image velocimetry (PIV) showed that at the turbine inlet (or the outlet of the 90° bend pipe), two counter rotating vortices, which are also known as Dean vortices, weaken and eventually vanish during the acceleration phase, but the vortices re-appear again during the deceleration phase over a pulse period [13]. The hysteresis loop in the turbine performance map measured under 90° bend pipe setup appears differently from the one measured under straight pipe setup, but the time-averaged performance maps between the two setups do not exhibit significant differences [13]. Although the works by Kalpakli et al. [13] provided us some insights into the fundamental flow physics at turbine inlet and the combined effects of secondary flow and flow pulsation on turbine performance, the experimental investigations still represent the basic scientific research from the engine application point of view due to the simplification of upstream geometry. Consequently, researchers like Marelli et al. [14] and Lyttek et al. [15] strived towards assessing the turbine performance with more advanced test facility. By using cylinders head equipped with Variable Valve Actuation (VAA) system as pulse generator, in combination with an exhaust manifold at the downstream of the pulse generator, unsteady turbine inflow conditions closer to the real situations could be achieved [14], [15]. The experiment setup also enables the investigation of turbine performance under different pulse frequency, amplitude and shape, by controlling the valve

stroke and opening speed [14], [15]. It is worth to note that although the aforementioned studies have included more realistic turbine inflow conditions, highly non-isothermal flow characteristic and heat loss phenomenon as present in the IC engines are still missing because of relatively low working air temperature (400 K and 300 K as reported in Refs. [14] and [15], respectively).

In order to reproduce the on-engine flow and thermodynamic characteristics at the turbine inlet, some researchers feed the turbine directly with the hot and pulsatile exhaust gas from engine combustion. A direct way to achieve this is via the so called on-engine test, in which the exhaust manifold and the turbocharger are mounted on an IC engine (e.g., see Refs. [1], [16]). Alternatively, one could remove the original turbocharger from the IC engine, and use the IC engine solely as pulse generator to feed the turbine with hot and pulsatile exhaust gas via an upstream exhaust manifold [17]. Note that although this type of setups allows researchers to replicate the realistic flow and thermodynamics complexity, as well as the heat loss phenomenon in the turbine, measurements of the instantaneous thermo-fluid parameters in the turbocharging circuit of an automotive engine remain challenging [18]–[20]. Experiment difficulties could be attributed to low frequency response of the sensors, sensitivity of measurement results to sensor positioning due to highly 3D flow fields, measurement procedures, data filtering techniques, etc (see, e.g. Refs. [18], [19]). Furthermore, due to space constraint and harsh operating environment, flow visualization to enhance the understanding of the associated flow physics is also technically challenging.

Generally, automotive engine system optimization process involves performance computations over many engine operating points by iterative engine simulations. This has driven the development of various zero- (0D) and one-dimensional (1D) models with different degree of modeling complexity to provide fast and low-cost performance prediction tools. These modelling approaches are often based on the 1D mass, momentum and energy conservation equations for a pipe flow, in conjunction with turbocharger performance maps measured under steady continuous flow scenario. It is worth noting that 0D/1D models often require significant amount of calibration against experiment data (e.g., see Refs. [19], [21]). The validity of the models is highly dependent on the correlation methods with experiment measurements, empirical aerothermodynamic loss models, geometrical representations, etc (e.g., see Refs. [2], [19]). Although a well experimentally calibrated 0D/1D model could potentially serve as a cost-effective tool in performance prediction, 3D flow physics associated with the high temperature pulse flow in the turbine could not be analysed.

Discussions above suggest that there are relatively little efforts to understand the effects of secondary flow and flow unsteadiness under realistic on-engine conditions on turbine performance. Furthermore, there is also limited knowledge about how the pulsating nature of the exhaust gas affects the dynamics of heat transfer, probably attributed to pulsating flow measurement difficulties under hot conditions, as well as computational hardware and time constraints [20].

Although the turbine CFD work with the integration of exhaust manifold by Hellström and Fuchs [12] provided us some insights into the flow features at the turbine inlet, adiabatic assumption was made and hence the effects of flow pulsation combined with secondary flow on heat transfer remain unclear. In addition, quantification of the effects of upstream exhaust manifold on turbine performance is missing in the numerical study by Hellström and Fuchs [12].

Motivated by the research gaps mentioned above, we aimed to investigate the effects of upstream exhaust manifold on turbine performance, including the impact on heat transfer. Prior to this study, the influences of exhaust manifold on the turbine power, aerothermodynamic losses and heat loss were quantified by using the flow exergy methodology [22]. This study mainly focused on the impacts of the exhaust manifold on the unsteady flow field in the turbocharger turbine. An overview of the research strategy employed in this study is depicted in Figure 1. Two types of CFD models were set-up, i.e. a model with an exhaust manifold integrated to the upstream of turbine (hereinafter called the full model), and a model which excludes the exhaust manifold (hereinafter called the simple model). Firstly, with the time-varying outputs from an experimentally calibrated 1D engine simulation model with GT-POWER (hereinafter called the 1D model) as boundary conditions, Detached Eddy Simulation (DES) was performed on the full model. Next, the flow variables predicted by the full model at the turbine inlet (i.e. the interface between exhaust manifold and scroll) were imposed as the inlet boundary conditions for a separate simulation with the simple model. Lastly, the flow fields and the turbine power predicted by the full and the simple models were compared and discussed. Note that due to the lack of detailed knowledge about the 1D model's calibration work by our industry partner, we focused our study toward the understanding of flow physics in the full and the simple models.

Figure 1. Overview of research strategy

METHODOLOGY

The investigated object in this study is a nozzleless single-entry scroll and wastegated turbocharger radial turbine used in a 2.0 litre 4-cylinder spark-ignition (SI) passenger car engine. The overall computational domain and grid for the full model are depicted in Figure 2, and the

detailed geometry and grid of the rotor are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Computational domain and mesh of full model. The simple model has identical mesh characteristics, but without the exhaust manifold

Figure 3. Geometry and grid of the rotor. The sketch of velocity triangle at the rotor's inlet shows the sign convention of the relative inflow angle β_1 to be discussed in this study

The full model has an exhaust manifold which consists of four pipes with different lengths and curvatures, a scroll, a deeply scalloped rotor with twelve blades, a diffuser and an outlet duct. Detailed geometrical features like the tip gap and the back face gap were modelled to account for the flow leakage and the windage losses, respectively. The waste gate was excluded from the model because our study focused on the part-load engine operation at 1500 rpm engine speed, in which the waste gate is closed and no exhaust gas is bypassed. The exhaust manifold, the scroll, the rotor and the diffuser were discretized by polyhedral grid. As we expect smaller scale flow structures in the rotor and its downstream diffuser as compared to the exhaust manifold and the scroll, we doubled the grid resolution in the rotor and the diffuser regions as compared to the upstream regions. At the region far from the rotor, i.e. the outlet duct, we gradually stretched

the grid from the diffuser-outlet duct interface with hexahedral cells (not shown in Figure 2). Note that the outlet boundary is located far from the rotor outlet, i.e. about thirteen rotor outlet diameters from the rotor-diffuser interface. This is intended to minimize the direct influence of imposed boundary conditions at the outlet to the predicted flow fields in the rotor region, as the CFD work by Palfreyman et al. [5] showed significant degree of pressure damping near the rotor's trailing edges region due to its close proximity to the outlet boundary in their computational model. At the near-wall region, prism layers with 1.1 stretching factor were employed to capture the flow gradients in the wall normal direction for all components.

Prior to this study, we investigated the influence of grid resolution in the core flow and the near-wall regions based on a hot gas stand continuous flow scenario. We compared the total-to-static pressure ratio to the experimental data measured by our industrial partner at their hot steady flow gas stand, and evaluated the numerical convergence of the predicted turbine torque, heat transfer rate, statistical mean and fluctuation of velocity and temperature, as well as the specific kinetic energy spectra. Readers are referred to Lim [23] for details. From the grid sensitivity study as reported in Lim [23], we concluded that a full model with about 9 million cells using 12 prism layers at the near-wall region to achieve y^+ (non-dimensional wall distance) less than unity is appropriate. Note that although the simple model has the exhaust manifold excluded in the computational domain, it has identical grid characteristics as the full model.

Strong coupling of thermal and flow dynamics is expected in the highly non-isothermal pulsatile flow involving heat transfer. Therefore, the conservation equations for mass, Navier-Stokes momentum and energy were solved simultaneously by using a fully compressible coupled CFD solver (i.e. Star-CCM+ by Siemens). The pressure and the internal energy of a fluid element were related to the independent thermodynamic state variables of density ρ and temperature T by using the thermal and caloric equations of state, respectively. We have previously verified and validated the solver in unsteady flow simulations of centrifugal compressors under adiabatic assumption (e.g., see Refs. [24]–[26]). Solver verification with regards to the heat transfer was done by conducting a series of sensitivity studies on grid, time-step, turbulence model, etc, and readers are referred to Lim [23] for details.

In pulsatile turbine flow, a wide range of flow length scales is expected to present spatially over a pulse period. In such scenario, solving all the flow details would be costly, but approximating the flow with lower order turbulence model might restrict our understanding of the associated flow physics. Therefore, a hybrid turbulence modeling approach, i.e. Detached Eddy Simulation (DES), was employed to close the system of conservation equations. The hybrid method computes the attached flow region with the two-equation SST (Shear Stress Transport) $k - \omega$ Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) turbulence model [27], while massively separated region was calculated by the Large Eddy Simulation (LES) with the standard Smagorinsky subgrid-scale (SGS) model.

Improved Delayed DES (IDDES) formulated by Shur et al. [28] was adopted to handle the RANS-LES interface. Note that we opted for DES in our study over unsteady RANS (uRANS) because in a turbulence model sensitivity study under continuous flow scenario, we found that although there is no significant difference in predicting the turbine global performances between the two modeling approaches, specific kinetic energy spectra showed that uRANS is more dissipative as compared with DES in regions with high degree of flow mixing flow [23]. This indicates that DES is potentially a more appropriate modeling approach as we aimed to understand the flow physics in addition to evaluate the turbine global performances.

The motion of the rotor was modeled by using a sliding mesh technique, i.e. the rotor is rotated physically by an angular angle at each physical time-step. Second order implicit-time stepping method, which uses a few inner iterations to converge the solution at each physical time-step, was employed. We used a constant physical time-step which corresponds to about ten steps per blade passage (equivalent to approximately three degrees per physical time-step), in combination with five inner iterations. With the available computational resource, this set-up was proven capable of solving the desired flow dynamics up to the time-scale associated with the unsteady blade passing event without significant damping of the specific kinetic energy [23]. As for the convection terms, we chose a hybrid second-order upwind/bounded central differencing scheme. This is because hybrid scheme could potentially provide us the best out of the two schemes, i.e. lower dispersive error in RANS region with the central differencing scheme, and better preservation of turbulent kinetic energy in the LES region, in addition to more computational robustness with the bounded central-differencing scheme.

Exhaust gas was approximated as air that obeying the ideal gas law. We used the Sutherland's law to account for the spatial and temporal dependency of molecular dynamic viscosity μ_{mol} and molecular thermal conductivity k_{mol} to temperature. Moreover, NASA fourth order polynomial function was used to model the specific heat capacities at constant pressure c_p of air.

BOUNDARY AND INITIAL CONDITIONS

An operating point on the engine part load curve that corresponding to 1500 rpm engine speed was investigated in this study. For the CFD works associated with the full model, the outputs from the 1D model (provided by industry partner) were used as the boundary conditions. At the inlet boundaries (i.e. the exhaust ports; see Figure 2), mass flow rate at the exhaust ports \dot{m}_{in} as shown in Figure 4(a) was imposed as according to the firing order 2-1-3-4. Note from Figure 4(a) that during the firing from a particular exhaust port, there is small backflow at other exhaust ports, as indicated by negative \dot{m}_{in} . At the instances of inflow ($\dot{m}_{in} > 0$), total temperature $T_{t,in}$ as shown in Figure 4(b) was imposed at the inlet boundaries, but extrapolated values of $T_{t,in}$ from the neighbouring inner cells were imposed at instances of outflow (i.e. $\dot{m}_{in} < 0$). Synthetic Eddy Method (SEM) was employed to generate turbulent inlet

(a) Inlet ports mass flow rate

(b) Inlet ports total temperature

(c) Outlet absolute static temperature and rotor's rotational speed

Figure 4. Boundary conditions for the full model [22]. The time on the horizontal axis is normalized by the period of engine cycle

conditions [29]. Inflow was assumed to be normal to and uniformly distributed over the inlet boundary planes with constant turbulent intensity of 5%, in which the value was estimated from a fully developed pipe flow. At the outlet boundary plane, time-varying static pressure P_{out} as plotted in Figure 4(c) was imposed (see the solid line). The

rotor was rotated as according to the time-dependent rotational speed Ω_z depicted by the dashed line in Figure 4(c). All walls were treated as smooth and non-permeable, with no-slip condition. As for the thermal boundary conditions, constant wall temperatures $T_w = 1073.15 K$ was imposed to the exhaust manifold and the scroll, but $T_w = 928.8 K$ was imposed to the diffuser and the outlet duct. The rotor was treated adiabatically. Note that the aforementioned wall temperatures are the time-averaged values predicted by the 1D model. As the time-scale associated with the solid materials thermal inertia is larger than that of the flow pulsation [1], constant wall temperature assumption for the thermal boundary condition is thought to be reasonably valid.

(a) Turbine inlet mass flow rate

(b) Turbine inlet total temperature (mass averaged)

Figure 5. Inlet boundary conditions for the simple model. The data is extracted from the exhaust manifold-scroll interface plane of the full model CFD. The time on the horizontal axis is normalized by the period of engine cycle. The data is ensemble averaged based on 3 engine cycles

As depicted in Figure 1, the inlet boundary for the simple model corresponds to the turbine inlet or the exhaust manifold-scroll in the full model. From the full model, time-varying mass flow rate \dot{m}_T and mass weighted average total temperature $T_{t,T}$ at the exhaust manifold-scroll

interface were monitored, as shown in Figure 5. These values were imposed as the inlet boundary conditions for the simple model. Inflow was assumed to be perpendicular to and uniformly distributed over the inlet boundary, and hence no secondary flow presents at the turbine inlet. Other boundary conditions (i.e. P_{out} , Ω_z , and wall thermal conditions) for the simple model were identical to the full model discussed before. From Figure 5 we observe good periodicity in the monitored data, with slight differences in the peak amplitude over an engine cycle. Therefore, we arbitrarily chose only a single pulse of the firing from port 2 to reduce the total physical time of simulations with the simple model. It is worth noting that the geometrical set-up, as well as the aforementioned simulations with only a single pulse (instead of the entire engine cycle period with four pulses) for the simple model are similar to most of the pulsatile turbine flow simulation practices found in open literature (see, e.g. Refs. [5], [7], [30]).

Prior to the transient simulations with full model, steady-state RANS simulations based on the SST $k - \omega$ turbulence model with mixing plane stationary-rotating interfaces were performed on the full model. Here, the time-averaged values of the time-varying data depicted in Figure 4 were used as the boundary conditions for the steady-state RANS simulations of the full model. DES computations of the full model were then initialized by the aforementioned steady-state RANS flow field. As for the computation with simple model, solutions from the last time-step of the DES simulations with full model were used as initial conditions. The total physical time of the simulations corresponded to four engine cycles and four pulse periods for the full and the simple models, respectively. In the first engine cycle/pulse period, numerical oscillation in solutions due to prescribed initial conditions was observed, and hence only data from the second engine cycle/pulse period onward was used for the analyses in this study. Ensemble averaging based on three engine cycles/pulse periods was performed to generate all the quantitative plots (i.e. Figures 5, 8 and 9) in this study. However, ensemble averaging was not performed to generate the contour plots of the flow fields involving 2D sectional planes (i.e. Figures 6 and 7) in this study because the variations of the plots from one engine cycle/pulse period to another were found to be insignificant. Since comparing the instantaneous data of different cases does not affect the outcomes of the qualitative flow field analyses presented in this study, we could reduce the overall computational cost by avoiding saving huge amount of flow field data on 2D sectional planes, as well as the cost associated with data post-processing.

All simulations were run on a Cray XC40 system, which has 53632 cores in total (1676 nodes with 32 cores/node). With 320 cores, the simulation time that corresponds to an engine cycle period of 1500 rpm engine speed was about 48 hours for the full model. Since we only simulated a single pulse from firing of the exhaust port 2 for the simple model, the computational time of a simple model was about a quarter of the full model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 6 shows the instantaneous static temperature distribution in the scroll for the full model. The static temperature is normalized by the imposed wall temperature on the scroll, i.e. $T_w = 1173.15 K$. The time instances A & D, and B & C correspond to the acceleration and deceleration phases at identical mass flow rate at the turbine inlet $\dot{m}_T = 0.0567 kg/s$ and $0.1134 kg/s$, respectively, as denoted in Figure 5. Streamlines are overlapped on the contour plots to visualize the flow patterns.

In general, it is clear from Figure 6 that in addition to spatially non-uniform temperature distribution around the scroll, secondary flow is observed in the scroll as a result of exhaust gas blowing from the exhaust manifold. During the initial exhaust gas blow down at time A as shown in Figure 6 (a), high temperature gas fills the region of the scroll from the turbine inlet to about $\theta = 90^\circ$. The remaining circumferential portion of the scroll has lower temperature gas, which entered the scroll at earlier time. There are reversing vortices near the turbine inlet at the mid horizontal plane from time A to D, indicating reversed flow into the adjacent pipes of the exhaust manifold which are not firing momentarily. From Figure 5(a), momentarily drop in the mass flow rate at the turbine inlet is observed before time A, and this suggests that reversed flow is most significant at the very beginning of the exhaust gas blow down.

In the longitudinal sectional planes of the scroll, large scale rotating vortices are clearly observed. The number of vortices, and the rotating direction of the vortices change in both space and time. For example, two counter rotating vortices appear in the longitudinal plane of $\theta = 90^\circ$ at time A. However, these counter rotating vortices transform into a single large vortex as time proceeds to B. It is worth noting that the secondary flow structures in the longitudinal planes seem to diminish as θ increases. At about $\theta \approx 270^\circ$, the flow pattern in the longitudinal plane is observed to be dominant by radially inward streamlines, which is similar to the expected flow pattern in the continuous flow scenario.

Despite the presence of large scale vortices in the longitudinal cross-sectional planes as discussed above, relatively good radially inward streamlines are observed near the outlet of the scroll. This suggests that the converging sectional area of the scroll towards the inner radii might play a role in dampening flow fluctuations in the longitudinal direction, i.e. along the z-rotational axis.

Figure 7 shows the instantaneous static temperature superimposed with streamline patterns in the scroll for the simple model. When the exhaust manifold is absent, it is obvious that the streamlines follow the geometrical passage of the scroll from the turbine inlet to the outlet of the scroll in both circumferential and radial directions at all time instances. Large scale vortices as observed in the full model is not present in the simple model. It is interesting to note that although the CFD set-up for the simple model is similar to that of the common practice found in open literature, the streamline patterns observed in the longitudinal sectional planes in this study is different from that of observed in other studies. For examples, in the pulsatile flow turbine

(a) Time A: accelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.0567 \text{ kg/s}$

(b) Time B: accelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.1134 \text{ kg/s}$

(c) Time C: decelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.1134 \text{ kg/s}$

(d) Time D: decelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.0567 \text{ kg/s}$

Figure 6. Static temperature at different time instances in the scroll for the full model. Streamlines are overlaid on the contour plots to show the flow pattern. See Figure 2 for the locations of sectional planes. A, B, C and D correspond to the time instances depicted in Figure 5

(a) Time A: accelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.0567 \text{ kg/s}$

(b) Time B: accelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.1134 \text{ kg/s}$

(c) Time C: decelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.1134 \text{ kg/s}$

(d) Time D: decelerating phase of $\dot{m}_T = 0.0567 \text{ kg/s}$

Figure 7. Static temperature at different time instances in the scroll for the simple model. Streamlines are overlaid on the contour plots to show the flow pattern. See Figure 2 for the locations of sectional planes. A, B, C and D correspond to the time instances depicted in Figure 5

CFD works with inlet straight pipe mounted to the upstream of turbine inlet, Lee et al. [31] reported small degree of dean vortices in the scroll with circularly symmetric longitudinal sectional shape, while Yang et al. [32] observed small vortices in the scroll with trapezoidal longitudinal cross section. Both Lee et al. [31] and Yang et al. [32] argued that the geometrical shape of the scroll and the radial pressure gradient could influence the flow structures observed in the longitudinal sectional planes.

Figure 8. Time varying turbine power. Only the data of firing from port 2 is shown for the full model for comparison purpose. The data is ensemble averaged based on 3 engine cycles and pulse periods for the full and simple models, respectively

It is noteworthy that there are no secondary flow streamlines and non-uniformity of static temperature at the turbine inlet plane (section A-A) for the simple model. This is because we have prescribed the inflow to be perpendicular to the turbine inlet plane with spatially uniform flow distribution. Also, as some finite time is needed to fill the scroll with exhaust gas, we see higher temperature gas, followed by lower temperature gas in the circumferential direction during the accelerating phase at time A and B in Figure 7(a) and (b). Comparing to the full model, more time is needed to fill the scroll with hot gas in the scroll for the simple model, as can be seen from (a) and (b) of Figure 6 and 7, respectively. Due to the simplification of the inlet boundary conditions, the effective flow area at the turbine inlet (section A-A) for the simple model is larger, as compared to the full model. This is evident as we observe that the mass flow is only concentrated on the upper right portion in Figure 6(a) for the full model, while spatially uniform mass flow over the whole turbine inlet is observed in Figure 7(a) for the simple model. Since the mass flow at the turbine inlet at a specified time during the accelerating phase is similar for both models, higher convective gas velocity is expected, and therefore hot exhaust gas fills the scroll and reaches the rotor for power extraction faster in the full model, as compared to the simple model. As a result, the full model exhibits higher gradient during the accelerating phase in the time-varying turbine power plot (i.e. $d\dot{W}_T/dt$), as compared to the simple model in Figure 8. Note from Figure 6(c) & 7(c) (time C) and Figure 6(d) &

7(d) (time D) that the emptying process (decelerating phase) also occurs at a lower rate for the simple model when compared to the full model, but its effect on the time-varying turbine power is not as significant as during the filling process (accelerating phase).

From the discussions above, it is obvious that the flow field in the scroll is significantly influenced by the upstream exhaust manifold. Furthermore, the filling and emptying phenomenon of the scroll is also affected by the presence of exhaust manifold, which in turn affect the behaviour of the time-varying turbine power, especially during the filling/accelerating phase. These results imply that analysis of the unsteady behaviours and flow features in the scroll with an upstream straight pipe set-up (e.g., see Refs. [5], [10], [33], [34]) should be interpreted with care as the fundamental flow physics in the scroll differ with the presence of exhaust manifold.

In order to investigate the effects of secondary flow in the scroll due to the presence of upstream exhaust manifold on the inflow to the rotor, the space-time diagrams of relative flow angle at the rotor's inlet (hereinafter called relative inflow angle β_1), as depicted in Figure 9, are constructed. At about 2 mm upstream to the blade leading edge at the rotor mid span, uniformly distributed stationary probe points at 10° interval as shown in Figure 2 were used to monitor β_1 at each physical time-step during the simulations. If the tangential component of the relative inflow velocity $w_{\theta 1}$ has the same direction as the circumferential speed u_1 , β_1 is defined to be positive. β_1 is negative in the opposing scenario. A pictorial definition of β_1 could be found in the sketch of velocity triangle in Figure 3.

An overview of the spatial and temporal variations of β_1 over a complete engine cycle for the full model is depicted in Figure 9(a). Four alternating horizontal stripes of low and high β_1 could be observed. These stripes correspond to the periodic flow at the turbine inlet as seen in Figure 5, due to the sequential firing from different exhaust ports. During the time duration of high \dot{m}_T (e.g. $t/t_{cycle} \approx 0.05 - 0.1$), in which the available energy to the turbine is high, β_1 is positive and far from the optimum values of -20° to -30° reported by Wolley et al. [35] and Yeo et al. [10]. Optimum rotor's inflow condition of $\beta_1 = -20^\circ$ to -30° only occurs over a short fraction of time over the whole engine cycle, and this occurs when the available energy to the turbine is low at low turbine inlet mass flow rate. This result suggests that the inflow conditions at the rotor's inlet is sub-optimum under most of the time instances. Similar findings were also reported by Padzillah et al. [6].

Since the data of firing from port 2 is used as the boundary conditions for the simple model, it is therefore relevant to compare the space-time diagram of the simple model to that of the full model during the firing from port 2. When comparing Figure 9(b) and (c), we observe more temporal and spatial variations of β_1 in the full model, as compared to the simple model. This is attributed to the secondary flow in the scroll due to the presence of exhaust manifold, as discussed before. At some instances when the

Figure 9. Space-time diagram of the relative flow angle β_1 at rotor's inlet. The time at the vertical axis is normalized by the period of engine cycle. A, B, C and D correspond to the time instances depicted in Figure 5. See Figure 3 for the sign convention of β_1 . The data is ensemble averaged based on 3 engine cycles and pulse periods for the full and simple models, respectively

turbine inlet mass flow rate \dot{m}_T is low (e.g. $t/t_{cycle} \approx 0.16 - 0.18$), both models exhibit very negative relative inflow angle (i.e. $\beta_1 < -90^\circ$). From the sign convention of β_1 as defined in the sketch of velocity triangle in Figure 3, $|\beta_1| > 90^\circ$ implies the occurrence of reverse flow, i.e. the gas flow radially outward instead of radially inward as in the normal turbine operation. Note that at a particular time instance, reverse flow does not occur at the inlet of all blade passages, as $\beta_1 < -90^\circ$ is not observed at every circumferential location in the space-time diagrams.

It is found that the instances when $\beta_1 < -90^\circ$ coincide with the instances when negative turbine power is observed in Figure 8. Therefore, the reverse flow phenomenon in some of the rotor's blade passage could potentially lead to turbine windmilling at low mass flow rate. It is worth to note that the mass flow rate at the turbine inlet remains positive at all time ($\dot{m}_T > 0$; see Figure 5(a)). This suggests that the observed reverse flow here is limited to the proximity of the scroll-rotor interface, the rotor and probably also in its downstream components.

It is interesting to note that in the study by Padzillah et al. [6], the experimentally measured turbine torque exhibits negative values at some time instances, but this windmilling phenomenon was not predicted by the CFD. Close proximity of outlet boundary to the rotor's trailing edges in their computational model, in addition to imposing constant atmospheric pressure at the outlet boundary, would limit the degree of freedom in the prediction of pressure changes over the rotor, which in turn suppressing the development of reverse flow in CFD. Therefore, it is relevant to confirm this hypothesis by performing sensitivity study about the location of outlet boundary in future, as Galindo et al. [7] also addressed the importance of allowing certain pressure variation at the rotor's outlet in pulsatile flow turbine simulation.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we showed that the exhaust manifold has significant influence on the fundamental thermo-fluid physics on its downstream scroll. Customary state of the art in the pulsatile flow turbine research with a set-up that ignoring the presence of exhaust manifold could not capture the unsteady large-scale vortices in the scroll. Furthermore, the convective velocity of the gas is shown to be higher in the model with exhaust manifold, which influencing the filling and emptying processes in the scroll and the behavior of time-varying turbine power. Therefore, analyses of the flow field, unsteadiness and aerothermodynamic losses in the scroll based on a set-up that excluding the exhaust manifold should be interpreted with care.

Through temporal and spatial analyses of the flow fields at the rotor's inlet, we have shown the phenomenon of reverse flow in the rotor blade passages during the instances of low mass flow rate. This is thought to cause turbine windmilling at low mass flow rate. Furthermore, we also observed that the inflow angle of the rotor deviates from the optimum range of -20° to -30° over a large fraction of duration over an engine cycle/pulse period, which might

lead to poor available energy extraction by the turbine as reported in previous study [22]. This finding is similar to the result reported by researchers like Padzillah et al. [6].

This study depends on the experimentally calibrated 1D engine simulation model as the boundary conditions to the CFD works. Ideally, time-varying boundary conditions provided by direct experiment measurements are desirable, but this ideal approach is often limited by the current state of the art in the measurement techniques under hot and pulsatile flow scenario. Nevertheless, the outcomes of this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the thermo-fluid physics associated with the presence of upstream exhaust manifold, which is often neglected in other studies. Furthermore, this study also provides the missing puzzle pieces associated with the customary pulsatile flow turbine research approach of ignoring the upstream exhaust manifold, and increase the consciousness about the pros and cons of current state of the art.

Although this study focused on a particular geometry configuration and a specified exhaust valve strategy, the scope of the study could be extended to various exhaust manifold and scroll design, as well as different exhaust valve strategies in the future. This would enhance our understanding on the parameters that influence the flow physics and performance, which could lead to improvement in the design methodology for pulsatile flow turbine.

NOMENCLATURE

T	Temperature	K
p	pressure	Pa
t	Time	s
k	Thermal conductivity	W/m-K
c_p	Specific heat at constant pressure	J/kg-K
y^+	Dimensionless wall distance	-
\dot{W}	Power	W
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate	kg/s
w	Relative velocity	m/s
c	Absolute velocity	m/s
u	Rotor velocity	m/s

Greek letters

ρ	Density	kg/m ³
μ	Viscosity	kg/s-m
Ω	Rotational speed	radian/s
β	Relative flow angle	°
α	Absolute flow angle	°

Subscripts

w	Wall
t	Total/stagnation quantity
T	Turbine
1	Rotor inlet
z	z -axis, i.e. direction of rotational axis
<i>cycle</i>	Engine cycle
θ	Tangential component
m	Meridional component

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